

branch without significantly increasing those on the secondary branch.

Medullary cavity was positively correlated with the number of inner and outer vascular bundles and with culm diameter. These characters may be utilized as selection criteria. Culm thickness had no relation with any of the characters, and had minimum variability.

Acc. nos. 103350, 103443, 102198, 103997, 104001, and 104003, with higher numbers of primary branches, spikelets on primary branches, and inner and outer vascular bundles and larger culm

Table 2. Relationship between 10 panicle characters in *O. glaberrima*. IRRI, 1987.

	PB	SB	SPB	SSB	TSP	IVB	OVB	CD	MC
SB	-0.46ns								
SPB	0.96**	-0.34ns							
SSB	-0.46ns	0.99**	-0.35ns						
TSP	0.56*	0.45ns	0.68**	0.44ns					
IVB	0.60*	0.03ns	0.62**	0.02ns	0.61*				
OVB	0.54*	0.04ns	0.55*	0.02ns	0.54*	0.85**			
CD	0.08ns	0.40ns	0.22ns	0.39ns	0.51*	0.49ns	0.55*		
MC	0.18ns	0.35ns	0.31ns	0.32ns	0.55*	0.67**	0.65**	0.87**	
CTh	0.05ns	0.16ns	0.11ns	0.18ns	0.25ns	-0.04ns	0.07ns	0.28ns	-0.15ns

diameter and medullary cavity may be used in breeding for increased numbers of primary branches and numbers of

spikelets on the primary branches. We have made 50 crosses involving these parents for evaluation. □

***eui* gene for elongated uppermost internode transferred to indica rice**

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The *eui*, a recessive gene controlling the elongated uppermost internode in rice, was discovered by Drs. J. N. Rutger and H. L. Carnahan at Davis, California, USA. The gene nearly doubled the length of the uppermost internode, increased panicle length 12%, and had little or no effect on other internodes or

IR50-*eui* rice plant compared to IR50. IRRI, 1987.

Comparative performance of IR50-*eui* and IR50. IRRI, 1987 DS.

Trait	IR50- <i>eui</i>	IR50	Difference ^a
Days to flowering	84	83	
Height (cm)	110.7	64.3	+46.4**
Tillers (no./hill)	25	35	-10.0**
% <i>eui</i> tillers	91.0	0	+91.0**
Yield (g/plant)	18.1	22.3	- 4.2ns

^a ** = significant at 1% level based on *t*-test of mean values. ns = nonsignificant based on *t*-test of mean values.

plant characters. It is considered equivalent to a recessive tall trait.

If the gene were incorporated into the paternal parent of hybrid rice, this parent would be taller. A taller restorer parent would aid windblown pollen dispersal on the semidwarf male sterile female parent in hybrid seed production plots. The resulting F₁ hybrid would, however, be semidwarf. Additionally, a taller restorer parent would facilitate its removal before bulk harvest of the commercial hybrid seed borne on the male sterile parent.

This gene was originally identified in a japonica line having limited use in tropical hybrid rice breeding. Original *eui* genetic stock obtained from Dr. Rutger in 1982 was crossed with semidwarf indica restorer IR50. From the F₂ population of this cross, plants showing the uppermost elongated internode were backcrossed to IR50 three times. In every BCF₂ generation, we selected plants possessing *eui* trait and resembling IR50. The BC₃F₃ progenies homozygous for *eui* gene were

selected and designated IR50-*eui* (see figure). Compared with IR50, IR50-*eui* is significantly taller, has 90% tillers with *eui* trait, but somewhat lower tillering (see table). Yields are not statistically different. Seeds of IR50-*eui* are available at IRRI.

5460ps: indica photosensitive genic male-sterile rice

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Fujian indica photosensitive genic male-sterile germplasm (FIPGMG) 5460ps, isolated from the spontaneous mutant of indica variety 5460, was released in Apr 1988 for developing two-line hybrid rice in China. 5460, as the restorer line for common three-line hybrid rice, was bred in 1983 from an early-maturing mutant (by radiation) of IR54.

Performance of 5460ps in Fujian, China, 1988.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Exserted stigma (%)	Resistance score				
							Blast	Bacterial blight	Brown planthopper	Bacterial leaf streak	Grassy stunt
5460ps	125	76.5	13.6	108.3	23.0	46.2	1	1	2	3	3
IR54	150	90.0	11.7	121.0	23.1	42.3	1	1	2	3	3

5460ps has high resistance to major diseases and insects, high-yielding agrocharacters, and good quality. Its

floral characters influencing outcrossing are also good (see table).

The critical stage of sterility-

transformation is about 10 Jul and fertility-transformation 10 Sep under conditions in Fuzhou (26°N). □

New japonica hybrid developed in China

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76-27A/PC312, a newly developed long-duration (130 d) japonica cross, has erect flag leaves, large panicles, and heavy grain. It shows moderate resistance to blast and bacterial blight. It has 90-cm plant height, 125 spikelets/panicle, and 70-80% seed set. A thousand grains weigh 26 g.

In yield trials in 1985 in 8 locations in northern Hunan, it averaged 6.3 t/ha (see table), 11.3% more than check Aiking 23. In farmers' fields in Shang-Tan in 1986, it outyielded Shan-you 63.

Seed production for the combination is easy; no split sowing is needed. It can yield 3 t hybrid seeds/ha. It is suitable for intermediate-fertility soils, for both single- or double-cropping seasons. □

Yield performance of japonica hybrid at 8 locations in Hunan, China, 1985.

Location	Yield (t/ha)		LSD	
	Hybrid ^a	Check	At 5%	At 1%
Changde	6.3	6.05	0.4	0.5
Yueyang	5.5	5.24	0.4	0.6
Miluo	6.5**	5.61	0.5	0.7
Taojiang	5.3	4.83	0.5	0.7
Xihu	7.4**	6.85	0.4	0.6
Huarong	6.3**	5.98	0.9	0.9
Wangcheng	6.8	6.23	0.3	0.6
Changsha	6.4**	4.62	1.4	1.6
Av	6.3**	5.68		

^a** = significant at 1%.

Effects of storage on rice germplasm viability

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In most breeding programs that lack storage facilities, germplasm is

maintained by periodical regeneration. Growing out all germplasm accessions every year takes extensive resources. We studied genotypic differences in germination under conventional storage conditions over 30 mo, to identify genotypes that retain viability longer.

Seeds of 24 varieties were obtained from the International Rice Germplasm Center in Nov 1984. Initial germination

Table 1. Ranges and means of temperature and relative humidity during storage, CRURRS, Hazaribag, India.

Month	Year	Relative humidity (%)		Temperature (°C)	
		Range	Mean	Range	Mean
Nov	1984	12 - 93	63.23 ± 1.87	7.0 - 29.0	19.50 ± 0.40
Dec	1984	14 - 88	52.31 ± 1.23	5.0 - 28.0	16.77 ± 0.24
Jan	1985	31 - 100	72.40 ± 2.25	7.0 - 27.0	16.35 ± 0.25
Feb	1985	32 - 100	63.02 ± 1.54	5.0 - 29.0	17.63 ± 0.28
Mar	1985	50 - 91	76.40 ± 1.18	13.0 - 38.0	25.64 ± 0.35
Apr	1985	28 - 84	57.42 ± 1.47	18.0 - 41.0	29.80 ± 0.37
May	1985	28 - 100	66.05 ± 1.83	20.0 - 43.0	30.27 ± 0.46
Jun	1985	55 - 100	84.67 ± 2.41	22.5 - 40.8	30.59 ± 0.37
Jul	1985	90 - 100	95.13 ± 0.52	22.1 - 32.0	26.25 ± 0.23
Aug	1985	88 - 100	96.03 ± 0.63	22.8 - 32.8	26.96 ± 0.24
Sep	1985	82 - 100	94.23 ± 0.92	21.8 - 32.2	26.40 ± 0.14
Oct	1985	87 - 100	84.23 ± 1.92	14.5 - 32.5	24.04 ± 0.50
Nov	1985	35 - 90	74.70 ± 2.02	10.4 - 28.0	20.19 ± 0.35
Dec	1985	53 - 100	79.56 ± 2.16	8.3 - 26.1	17.62 ± 0.36
Jan	1986	46 - 95	63.81 ± 1.83	5.9 - 26.5	16.31 ± 0.47
Feb	1986	44 - 94	62.29 ± 1.98	10.0 - 30.2	19.12 ± 0.30
Mar	1986	24 - 63	47.20 ± 1.83	13.9 - 39.5	24.92 ± 0.5 1
Apr	1986	29 - 71	48.97 ± 1.73	18.3 - 40.0	29.72 ± 0.38
May	1986	37 - 100	58.19 ± 2.59	19.5 - 40.0	29.42 ± 0.31
Jun	1986	35 - 96	70.73 ± 4.12	22.5 - 41.5	29.84 ± 0.63
Jul	1986	66 - 95	82.68 ± 1.25	22.4 - 32.3	26.04 ± 0.27
Aug	1986	65 - 92	81.23 ± 1.38	22.4 - 33.2	26.72 ± 0.18
Sep	1986	65 - 95	81.27 ± 1.72	20.0 - 33.3	26.07 ± 0.44
Oct	1986	41 - 100	79.44 ± 1.19	17.0 - 31.0	24.73 ± 0.29
Nov	1986	50 - 90	70.07 ± 1.68	13.5 - 29.5	21.41 ± 0.38
Dec	1986	53 - 94	71.03 ± 1.72	8.8 - 24.5	16.93 ± 0.26
Jan	1987	49 - 75	62.58 ± 1.40	6.9 - 24.3	15.67 ± 0.34
Feb	1987	56 - 68	61.29 ± 0.74	10.1 - 30.0	20.25 ± 0.37
Mar	1987	45 - 71	55.52 ± 1.20	14.0 - 35.8	24.36 ± 0.47
Apr	1987	37 - 15	52.03 ± 1.72	18.0 - 39.3	29.02 ± 0.34
May	1987	42 - 80	53.52 ± 1.85	18.5 - 41.0	30.54 ± 0.64